

A study: BRICS oilseeds consumptions Vs Exports

Parmod kumar

Assistant Prof, USB, Chandigarh University, Gharuan

ABSTRACT:

BRICS is the acronym used for five major nations in the world i.e. Brazil, Russia, India, China and South Africa. Coalition of these nations aims at improving agricultural, and infrastructural conditions of member nations. The present papers studies one of the major components from Agricultural field i.e Soybean oils, vegetable oils, Protein meals and other oilseeds. Consumption and Exports of Soybean oils, vegetable oils, Protein meals and other oilseeds by BRICS nations is studied from year 1993 to 2017 so that trend and relationship can be established between consumption and exports.

Keywords: BRICS, Oilseeds, Export, International trade, vegetable oil

INTRODUCTION:

BRICS is the combination of five major Economies which includes Brazil, Russia, India, China and South Africa. The main aim of BRICS is to help each member of this organization with regards to infrastructure, projects, Agriculture and Financial assistance. Out of that Agricultural development is the main agenda of BRICS. Annual Meeting of BRICS oftenly called as SUMMIT aims at preparing and executing of various plans for agricultural developments among BRICS members. With efforts of all the BRICS members, agricultural development is achieving new heights in international agricultural marketing. With the agricultural development foreign investment and foreign capital is increasing. Efforts are on from all BRICS members to contribute for peace, development and Agricultural stability in the entire world. BRICS members own 35 percent of farmland 41 percent of forest land and 30 percent of the grassland of the entire world.

Given the above the present paper aims at providing an insight into the consumption and Export of Oilseeds by BRICS members.

REVIEW OF LITERATURE

Paroda,R.S(2013) in his research paper “ Indian oilseed scenario: Chanllenges and Opportunities” has pointed out that in Indian scenario linking of various stake holders (Farmers, policy makers, NGOs etc) is a chanllenging task in order to improve the vegetable oil performance. Also he mentioned that a clear cut policy is required to bridge the yield gap and to increase oilseed production.

Hailegiorgis Biramo Allaro (2011) in his research papers titled “Export performance of oilseeds and its determinants in Ethiopia” found that has evaluated the amount of trends of oilseeds export performance in Ethiopia over the period 1974 to 2009. This study tells that that the trends of export performance by analysing prices (domestic and world), real output and nominal exchange rate. This study reveals that real output and exchange rate significantly influence oilseeds export performance.

O.G. Schmidt(1999) in his research paper “OILSEEDS: Post-harvest Operations” has investigated that there are certain major problems related to post harvest of oilseeds that includes producer price, cost of inputs, agricultural crediting etc. Smallholder farmers can not afford high yielding hybrid seeds. National agricultural research system could not fully satisfied the needs of the smallholder farmers.

OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY:

The main objective of the study comprises of

- To find the trend analysis of Soybean consumption, other oilseeds consumption, Protein mean consumption, Vegetable oils consumption, Soybean Exports, other oilseeds Exports, Protein mean Exports, Vegetable oils consumption.
- To find the relationship between Soybean consumption and Soybean Exports, other oilseeds consumption and other oilseeds Exports, Protein Meals consumptions and Protein Meals Exports, Vegetable Oils Consumption and Vegetable Oils Exports.
- To Fit a regression model for Soybean consumption on Soybean Exports, Oilseeds Consumption on Oilseeds Exports, Protein Meals Consumption and Protein Meals Exports, Vegetable Consumption and Vegetable Exports.

Hypothesis:

- (i) Null Hypothesis: Null hypothesis states that there is no relation between Soybean Consumption and Exports
i.e. H_0 : There is no relationship between Soybean Consumption and Soybean Exports
- (ii) Null Hypothesis: Null hypothesis states that there is no relation between Other oil seeds Consumption and Other oil seeds Exports
i.e. H_0 : There is no relationship between Other oil seeds Consumption and Other oil seeds Exports
- (iii) Null Hypothesis: Null hypothesis states that there is no relation between Protein Meals Consumption and Protein Meals Exports
i.e. H_0 : There is no relationship between Protein Meals Consumption and Protein Meals Exports
- (iv) Null Hypothesis: Null hypothesis states that there is no relation between Vegetable Oils Consumption and Vegetable oils Exports

i.e. H_0 : There is no relationship between Vegetable Oils Consumption and Vegetable Oils Exports

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY:

Research Methodology is a collection of techniques and methods which identifies and process information for analysis. Research methodology is a step by step procedure to conduct research.

Research Design : The present study is based on Correlation Research design which explains the relationship between variables taken for this topic is soybean, Protein meals, Vegetable oils and other oilseeds consumption and Exports.

Data collection: This research is based on Secondary data of BRICS nations from 1993 to 2017 based on soybean, Protein meals, Vegetable oils and other oilseeds consumption and Exports.

Tools and Techniques: Trend analysis and Correlation is used for analysis.

Data Analysis and Interpretation:

Trend Analysis for soybean Consumption and Soybean Exports: It has been observed that the soybean Consumption has an increasing trend in BRICS countries after year 1997. There was almost no change in consumption from Year 1993 to 1997.

Tend Anlysis for Soybean Exports: It has been observed that there is a fall in Exports for Soybean from 1993 to 1994. Then soybean Export increased from year 1994 to 1997. Again after small decrease there is gradual increase in soybean Exports. Then there is big jump in Exports from year 2011 to 2014.

Trend Analysis for Vegetable Oils Consumption and Vegetable Oils Exports: It has been observed that there is an increasing trend in Vegetable oils consumption for for BRICS countries from year 1993 to 2017. Whereas in Vegetable oils Exports are declined from Year 1993 to year 1995 and after increase in 1996 it is again decreased till 1999. Then there is steap rise from year 2000 to 2008. Then till 2017 there is increase and decrease at regular intervals.

Trend Analysis for other oil seeds Consumption and Other Oil seeds Exports: Trend analysis of Oil consumption shows that there is an upward trend in the consumption of Oil seeds for the BRICS nations. Trend analysis of other oil seeds exports shows an uneven trend.

Trend analysis of Protein Meals Consumption and Exports: Trend analysis of Protein meals consumption shows an increasing trend. Protein meals exports also shows an constant trend.

Relationship between Soybean Consumption and Export:

Correlations

		Soybean Consumption	Soybean Export
Soybean Consumption	Pearson Correlation	1	.971**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.000
	N	25	25
Soybean Export	Pearson Correlation	.971**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	
	N	25	25

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

Interpretation: Correlation coefficient between Soybean Consumption and Export is .971 which is very high degree of positive correlation. Also from the table it is shown that there is a significant relationship Soybean consumption and Soybean Export.

Relationship between Other oilseeds Consumption and Other oilseeds Exports:

Correlations

		Other oilseeds Consumption	Other oilseeds Export
Other oilseeds Consumption	Pearson Correlation	1	-.156
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.456
	N	25	25
Other oilseeds Export	Pearson Correlation	-.156	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.456	
	N	25	25

Interpretation: It is clearly visible from the table that there is very low degree of negative correlation. As per significant value also it is visible that the correlation between other oilseeds consumption and other oilseeds Exports are not significant.

Relationship between Vegetable oil consumption and Exports:

Correlations

		Vegetable oils Consumption	Vegetable oils Export
Vegetable oils Consumption	Pearson Correlation	1	.879**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.000
	N	25	25
Vegetable oils Export	Pearson Correlation	.879**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	
	N	25	25

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

Interpretation: Correlation coefficient between vegetable oils consumption and Vegetable oils Exports are very high. It shows that the correlation is significant between vegetable oils consumption and vegetable oils exports.

Relationship between Protein meals Consumption and Protein meals Exports:

Correlations

		Protein meals Consumption	Protein meals Export
Protein meals Consumption	Pearson Correlation	1	.886**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.000
	N	25	25
Protein meals Export	Pearson Correlation	.886**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	
	N	25	25

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

Interpretation: Correlation coefficient between protein meals consumption and Export is very high. Also it shows that the correlation is significant.

Conclusion: It has been observed that

1. There is an increasing trend in the consumption and exports of soybean, protein meals and vegetable oils for BRICS nations.
2. There is an increasing trend for Other oils seeds consumption. But there are huge variations in other oil seeds consumption.
3. There is positive and high degree of relationship between soybean, protein meals and vegetable oils consumption and Exports.
4. But there is no relation between Other oilseeds consumption and Exports.

REFERENCES:

Anonymous. (1989). The Vegetable Oil/Protein System in Kenya: Project Description. Working paper No. 2. Working Paper Series, Vegetable Oil/Protein System Project. Research and Extension Division, Egerton University, PO Box 536, Njoro, Kenya.

Anonymous. (1997). Vegetable Oils/Protein System Improvement Network (VOPSIN): final technical report, IDRC project file 93-8477. March 1997. Agricultural Research Foundation (AGREF), PO Box 39189, Nairobi, Kenya and the Common Market for Eastern and Southern Africa (COMESA), PO Box 30051, Lusaka, Zambia

CSO (2013), "National Accounts Statistics 2013", Central Statistics Office, Ministry of Statistics & Programme Implementation, Government of India, New Delhi, May 2013

GoI (2012), "*State of Indian Agriculture 2011-12*", Directorate of Economics and Statistics, Department of Agriculture and Cooperation, Ministry of Agriculture, Government of India, New Delhi.

Abate T (2006). Focusing Agricultural Research to Address Development Needs; the way I see it. In Abate, T.2006a

FAO (Food and Agricultural Organization) (2010). Food outlook.
<http://www.taas.in/documents/pub33.pdf>